

From Cyclones to Cybersecurity: A Call for Convergence in Risk and Crisis Communications Research

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Author Contributions: All authors worked together to co-conceive the study; AMR and RJG conducted the analyses; All authors wrote portions of the manuscript and edited the manuscript in its entirety.

Competing Interest Statement: The authors have no competing interests.

Keywords: hazard, disaster, domain, discipline, scholarship

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Abstract

Effective risk and crisis communication can improve health and safety and reduce harmful effects of hazards and disasters. A robust body of literature investigates mechanisms for improving risk and crisis communication. While effective risk and crisis communication strategies are equally desired across different hazard domains (e.g., natural hazards, cyber security), the extent to which risk and crisis communication experts utilize the “lessons learned” from scientific domains outside their own is suspect. Therefore, we hypothesized that risk and crisis communication research is siloed according to scientific disciplines at the detriment to the advancement of the field of risk communications research writ large. We tested this hypothesis by evaluating the disciplinarity of 5,264 published papers containing risk and crisis communication keywords using a combination of simple descriptive statistics, natural language processing, and hierarchical clustering. Finding that the risk communication research is siloed according to disciplinary lexicons, we present our findings as a call for convergence amongst our risk and crisis communication scholars to bridge across our silos. In so doing, we will increase our ability to affect transformative change in the efficacy of our risk and crises messages.

Significance Statement

Risk and crisis communication are imperatives for protecting human and environmental wellbeing in the face of myriad hazards and crises, ranging from cybersecurity to natural hazards. Consequently, risk and crisis communication are critical and active areas of research that cut across scientific domains and disciplines. However, risk and crisis communication scholars are communicating in silos, which has hampered the transfer of knowledge across hazard and crisis types. Scholarly advancements from one area of research are not reaching scholars working in other areas of research – despite the common goal of creating effective risk and crisis messages. The future of risk and crisis communication will be brighter if we break down these silos and build bridges across disciplines and domains.

Main Text

Introduction

Risk and crisis communication scholarship spans multiple hazard domains, such as natural hazards (e.g., hurricanes (1); flooding (2); earthquakes (3)); public health issues (e.g., pandemics(4) and cancer (5)); and national security (e.g., nuclear safety (6) and cybersecurity (7)). A ubiquitous theme across these studies is a call for more effective strategies and approaches to risk and crisis communication that increase human and environmental safety and well-being and mitigate deleterious effects of a disaster. Whereas hazard case studies and issue topics vary, the goal to improve health and safety and reduce harmful effects remains unwavering.

Risk and crisis communication scholars have expended tremendous effort to improve the efficacy of messages. Yet, despite advances in risk and crisis communication, societies across the globe continue to experience increases in the frequency, magnitude, and cost of natural disasters, public health crises, and national security issues (8). Now is a critical time to identify possible areas of improvement in how risk and crisis communication scholars operate.

Existing risk and crisis communication strategies embrace little in the way of a standard approach (one notable exception is identification of the target audience) and are pluralistic in theoretical grounding. For example, some approaches include message construction (e.g., (9, 10)) others focus more on processes (e.g., (11)). Some approaches invoke a mental models approach (e.g., (12)) while others mass communication theory (e.g., (13)). While all meritorious in and of themselves, as a whole they create a primordial soup of communication strategies and approaches through which practitioners must wade. In tandem, how we, as risk and crisis communication scholars, approach developing best practices and strategies may inadvertently be imposing our own structural challenges upon ourselves.

In this study, we focus on whether we, as risk and crisis communications researchers, may be contributing to the gap between disastrous effects of hazards and advances in risk and crisis communication—that of multiple approaches grounded in varying theories. Researchers are trained in a particular discipline, and often tethered to specific journals that share ontological and epistemological assumptions and lexicon. We explore whether we have created our own silos by the very nature of our academic disciplines and reward systems to publish in disciplinary journals. While we fully embrace the excellence of discoveries found in individual studies, the objective of this study is to explore whether we, as risk and crisis communication scholars, have imposed our own structural challenges upon ourselves.

To better understand if these structural challenges exist, we need to take stock of the state of this scholarship and develop some basic metrics that allow us to understand how the field of research has developed. These metrics include (i) the rate of risk and crisis communication publications over time, (ii) the count of these scholarly publications by journal outlet, and (iii) the distribution of these publications by STEM, social science, and humanities domains. We

predicted that (i) the field—as indicated by numbers of publications—has grown rapidly over the last two decades, (ii) publications are widely distributed across outlets, and (iii) publications are largely siloed according to the domain of research (STEM, social science, humanities).

For this investigation, we conducted an extensive literature search of risk and crisis communication publications from 2002-2021. We assessed prediction (i) by plotting numbers of publications and outlets on an annual basis; prediction (ii) by regressing the number of publications to the number of publication outlets on an annual basis. We assessed prediction (iii) using natural language processing to assign the “disciplinarity” of each publication; we then performed a cluster analysis to investigate if risk and crisis communications research is siloed, and if siloed, how so.

Materials and Methods

Our work identified a corpus of publications related to risk communication, and constructed a lexicon to quantify the extent to which a given discipline is reflected in a publication. An overview of the process publication identification and lexicon creation is shown in Figure 1.

Publication Identification.

Data.—Our discipline quantification process began with identifying a set of relevant risk communication publications. To assemble this corpus of publications, we first needed to compile a list of search terms (List 1).

These search terms were collected by finding all the keywords used in the publications of every issue of The Journal of International Crisis and Risk Communication Research (JICRCR)¹ that matched the following regular expression:

$$(\text{risk})|(\text{crisis})|(\text{hazard})|(\text{communica})|(\text{prepar}) \quad (1)$$

We retained all search terms that were present as keywords in two or more publications within JICRCR.

Collection of Publication Metadata. —We queried four different publication databases for each search term in List 1. These four databases were: Association for Computing Machinery Digital Library², PubMed³, Web of Science⁴, and IEEE Xplore⁵. For each publication returned from each search term query, we cataloged the following publication metadata (if it was provided by the database): Title, Outlet Title, Abstract, Keywords and Date.

Publications Versus Outlets

We conducted a simple linear regression on the number of publications with risk and crisis communication keywords versus the number of outlets (e.g., journals, conference proceedings) on an annual basis.

Discipline Lexicon

Creation of Discipline-Specific Lexicons.—To create discipline specific lexicons, we first identified 26 different disciplines across three domains. Domains and disciplines were chosen based on the expert opinion of our team. The domains are Humanities, Social Sciences and Science, Technology, Engineering and Math (STEM). The disciplines included in the Humanities domain are English Language, Foreign Language, History, Journalism, Media Studies and Religious Studies. The disciplines included in Social Sciences domain are Anthropology,

¹ <https://stars.library.ucf.edu/jicrcr/>

² <https://dl.acm.org/>

³ <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>

⁴ <https://www.webofscience.com/wos>

⁵ <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/>

Business, Communication, Education, Policy, Public Administration, and Sociology. The disciplines included in STEM are Astronomy, Biology, Chemistry, Computer Science, Earth Science, Engineering, Information Science, Mathematics and Physics.

For each discipline, we created a lexicon to enable us to quantify the extent to which the discipline is reflected in each publication. We call this measure the *disciplinarity* of a *publication_x* given a *discipline_y*. The process for our lexicon creation for a given discipline (discipline *y*) was as follows:

- Identify the Wikipedia page describing the *discipline_y*.
- Scrape the non-html text from the Wikipedia page for *discipline_y*.
- Once the Wikipedia page for each *discipline_y* has been scraped:
 - Compute the term frequency-inverse document frequency (TF-IDF) scores for each non-html term on the Wikipedia page of *discipline_y* with respect to all other disciplines.
 - Identify the terms with TF-IDF scores in the top 5% for *discipline_y*.
 - Put the identified terms (those TF-IDF scores in the top 5%) in rank order.
 - For the identified, rank-ordered terms for *discipline_y*, produce a normalized score for each term according to Equation 2. In Equation 2, *i* reflects the rank of the term being scored and *n* reflects the rank of the term with the lowest TF-IDF score (i.e. final rank).

$$\frac{(n + 1) - i}{n} \quad (2)$$

We employed TF-IDF to quantify the uniqueness of terms in each scraped Wikipedia page for each discipline with respect to the scraped Wikipedia page for all other disciplines. Briefly, TF-IDF consists of two parts, TF (term frequency) and IDF (inverse document frequency). For a given term (*t*) and a given discipline (*discipline_y*) from our set of disciplines (*disciplines*), it is defined by Equation 3.

$$tf(t, discipline_y) * idf(t, disciplines) \quad (3)$$

In this study, TF quantifies the frequency of a specific term (*t*) in the scraped Wikipedia page of a discipline (*discipline_y*) with respect to the total number of terms in the Wikipedia document for *discipline_y*, counting each occurrence of the same term separately (*M*). The TF portion of the TF-IDF calculation is shown in Equation 4.

$$tf(t, discipline_y) = \frac{f_{t, discipline_y}}{M} \quad (4)$$

In this study, IDF quantifies how unique a term (*t*) is to the scraped Wikipedia page associated with a discipline compared to all other scraped Wikipedia pages for other disciplines. IDF is the logarithmically scaled inverse fraction of the Wikipedia discipline documents that contain the term. It is obtained by dividing the total number of Wikipedia discipline documents (*|disciplines|*) by the number of Wikipedia discipline documents containing the term, and then taking the logarithm of that quotient. The TDF portion of the TF-IDF calculation is shown in Equation 5.

$$idf(t, disciplines) = \log \frac{|disciplines|}{\# \text{ of occurrences of } t \text{ in all disciplines}} \quad (5)$$

The TF-IDF scores within the lexicon of each discipline were ranked and normalized to control for potential bias from extremely unique terms. The normalization process ensured each lexicon had terms within the same value range (0.0 – 1.0) and guaranteed the values for each discipline lexicon were distributed uniformly. In combination, these methodological decisions enabled every publication to be scored for every discipline without any systemic disciplinary bias.

Measuring the disciplinarity of a publication

Next, each publication was scored to determine its *disciplinarity*. Recall, *disciplinarity* is the extent to which a *publication_x* reflects *discipline_y*. The computation of the disciplinarity of *publication_x* with respect to *discipline_y* is shown in Figure 2 and described in what follows.

- The collected metadata (i.e. title, outlet title, abstract and keywords) associated with *publication_x* were concatenated in a single string. We refer to this as the metadata string for *publication_x*.
- The metadata string for *publication_x* was scored with the normalized score lexicon for *discipline_y*. We refer to this the disciplinarity score of *publication_x* with respect to *discipline_y*.
- The disciplinarity score of *publication_x* with respect to *discipline_y* was calculated as the sum of the normalized scores for the terms in the metadata string in *publication_x* that appeared in the lexicon for *discipline_y* divided by the number of total terms in the metadata string for *publication_x*. If there were not any terms in the metadata string for *publication_x* that appeared in the lexicon for *discipline_y*, then *publication_x* was given a disciplinarity score of 0 with respect to *discipline_y*.

Thus, the belonging of a publication (*publication_x*) to each discipline (*discipline_y*) is the disciplinarity score for the publication with respect to each of the 26 disciplines.

Cluster Analysis

We conducted a hierarchical cluster analysis on the disciplinarity scores of all publications across all disciplines. We first scaled and centered the disciplinarity scores for all papers within each discipline because the normalized disciplinarity scores were highly variable among disciplines. We subsequently created a Euclidean distance matrix of those data and conducted hierarchical clustering with average linkage (i.e., unweighted pair group method with arithmetic mean [UPGMA]).

Threats to Validity

In this section we examine the threats to validity of this work as described by Campbell and Stanley (21) and Wohlin et al. (22). Specifically, we discuss Conclusion Validity, Content Validity, Internal Validity, Construct Validity, and External Validity, as well as Reliability as described by Yin (23). The evaluation of each of the threats to these specific types of validity are elaborated in the following bullets.

- *Content Validity* refers to how representative the selected measures cover the content domain. A potential source of bias here is the chosen set of databases. While the chosen set of databases reflect collections of publications across a variety of disciplines, they do not represent the entire universe of publication databases. In addition, we chose to only include publications since 2002. This choice was made so that our work reflects the current risk and crisis communication landscape. However, it also means our work is not generalizable to other time periods.
- *Internal Validity* refers to the possibility of having unwanted causal relationships. The use of Wikipedia to create our discipline lexicons is a potential threat to internal validity. While it has

become an established source of information, it only reflects a single description of each discipline and could have been modified by uninformed or nefarious parties.

- *Construct Validity* refers to the meaningfulness of measurements and the choices made regarding the selection of independent and dependent variables such that these variables are representative of the theory. Our study hinges on the idea that published papers and the language used therein provides a meaningful barometer of disciplinarity. Given our collective experiences and professional opinion, we do not anticipate this to be a meaningful threat to validity.
- *External Validity* refers to the ability to generalize results. As in most case studies, the ability to generalize results is limited due to the inability to randomly sample or to randomly assign subjects to groups. However, it can be argued that a narrower definition of external validity—ecological validity—the extent to which these findings approximate similar situations in other real-world environments, is likely to hold. We expect that other studies would find similar results if it scoured additional databases and journals, as we have searched four large, reputable databases that span domains and disciplines.
- *Reliability* refers to how dependent the process is on the researchers. The researchers compiled the list of disciplines and domains based on literature review and expert opinion. Different researchers may have devised slightly different discipline categories. While subtle differences may occur, we would not expect the magnitude of differences in discipline categories to substantively alter the results presented here.

Results

The volume of risk and crisis communications publications indicates that this is an active area of research. Over the course of the study period (2002-2021) alone, we identified 5,264 publications containing risk or crisis communication key words. The growth of this field of research is not stationary (Figure 3). Rather, the development of this literature has two distinct periods. During the period from 2002 to 2009, the field experienced sustained growth. During the period from 2010 to 2020, the volume of publications remained high but has stabilized.

From 2002 to 2009, both the number of topical publications and the number of outlets increased dramatically. Using the endpoints of this period to assess growth, the number of publications increased by a factor of 6.7 from 63 to 421 between 2002 and 2009; the number of outlets increased nearly six-fold from 32 to 190 over the same period. From 2010 to 2020, the number of publications has averaged 331.5 with limited fluctuation (standard deviation [SD] = 32.0). The number of outlets was similarly stable during this period, with an average of 164.4 outlets (SD of 12.7). Thus, from these results, we can assess the saliency of the scholarship on risk and crisis communication, given the cumulative increases of topical publications over time.

Many outlets exist for these scholarly publications. However, each of these outlets published few risk and crisis publications each year. Each outlet contained an average of 2.1 risk and crisis communications publications each year. This was consistent throughout the study period, despite the differences in rates of publications from 2002-2009 and 2010-2021 (t -value = 15.9 and P -value < $1e^{-11}$ on 1 and 17 degrees of freedom from a linear regression; Figure 4). This result indicates that the literature on risk and crisis communications is widely distributed throughout the literature throughout the study period.

Although risk and crisis communication scholars have expended considerable effort to publish a large volume of studies, risk and crisis communications researchers lack a common vocabulary for convergent research advances. Analysis of the academic literature on risk and crisis communication reveal distinct disciplinary silos. We had predicted that the academic papers from disciplines within the domains of the Humanities, Social Sciences, and STEM fields would fall into three distinct clusters. That is, we predicted that papers with language strongly associated with a discipline in the humanities would all share one common root node whereas papers with

strong Social Science language would originate from another common root node, and papers with strong STEM language would all be associated with yet another distinct root node. We found that all papers with strong STEM language clustered in the upper branches (Figure 5, purple) whereas papers with strong humanities language clustered in the lower branches (Figure 5, green). This clustering indicates that papers with high scores for STEM language had low scores for humanities language and vice versa. Only disciplines within the social science domain were dispersed among the upper (STEM-heavy) and lower (humanities-heavy) branches of the dendrogram, but even their positioning indicates some degree of siloing.

Closely related disciplines clustered together, reflecting ontologies among disciplines. Within the STEM domain for instance, the disciplines of information science and computer sciences clustered together, as did earth science and astronomy, and chemistry, biology, and physics. Likewise, within the humanities domain, religious studies and philosophy clustered together. Among the domains of the humanities and social sciences, closely related disciplines also clustered together; media studies clustered with communication, and history clustered with sociology, anthropology, and psychology. This presentation – closely related disciplines clustered together both within and across domains – suggest that the siloing in the risk and crisis communication literature does not follow the three domains perfectly, but the academic literature is nonetheless siloed, with distinct STEM and humanities domains, and social sciences attributed to each, likely along methodological lines (Figure 5).

Discussion

Our current work provides an important baseline for taking stock of the field of risk and crisis communications research. The benefits of this work are threefold. We have: (1) characterized the development and state of the scholarship on risk and crisis communication research, (2) identified metrics for this characterization, and (3) developed benchmarks for assessing the extent to which this field of research shifts towards (or away from) siloing can be assessed in the future.

With respect to the state of the field, our teams' collective experience working across the research areas of natural hazards, viral spillover, and cybersecurity led us to posit that the literature on risk and crisis communication was highly distributed and disconnected. Our findings indicate that discipline-specific silos do exist, and we characterize their nature. The ontogeny of these silos is understandable given the diversity of risk and crises that this literature addresses. However, these silos come at a cost; risks and crises occur across disciplines and domains. Consequently, funding agencies (e.g., National Science Foundation) are supporting convergent⁶ research and innovation ecosystems. We suggest that without convergent research among disciplines and domains, advancements cannot fully transcend domains. We posit that convergence in risk and crisis communications research include: a shared understanding of domains and disciplines; concepts that cut across case study idiosyncrasies; and a domain-agnostic lexicon. The resulting approach will be adopted more generally by communication scholars and practitioners (in line with the successful NSF-funded CONVERGE Facility (14)).

With respect to the metrics and methodology we employed herein to quantify the current state of convergence in the field of risk and crisis communication, the same metrics can be used to measure the state of the field in the future. We selected metrics that are intentionally straightforward, repeatable, and parsimonious to facilitate their re-use. The use of third party, objective materials to identify search terms and define discipline lexicons, is meant to provide clear and simple assessment of the field in an unbiased manner. We do not suggest that these metrics are an end; rather, they are an initial step towards characterizing the state of convergence of the scholarship in the field. In future work, we will explore using bibliometrics to measure the impact of research within and across silos. This strategy will quantify the extent to

⁶ <https://beta.nsf.gov/funding/learn/research-types/learn-about-convergence-research#definition>

which researchers within silos are aware of and acknowledging one another's work regardless of whether the language used in their publications is domain agnostic or domain specific.

With respect to the development of benchmarks for assessing how the field of risk and crisis communication progresses, our approach here can be used in the future to measure how the field is growing and the extent to which our scholarship is converging (or not). It is almost certain that there will be a large increase in publications in the coming years associated with the risk and crisis messaging during the COVID-19 pandemic. What is less certain is where these publications will be published and if they will be widely disbursed throughout the literature. As those data on publication rates become available, the approach and metrics utilized here provide a foundation for assessing exactly how the field is evolving – towards or away from a convergent lexicon. We now have a prototype frame for assessing improved convergence or increased siloing. For instance, if the field is moving towards convergence, we expect to see the ratio of publications to outlets to increase from 2.1:1 (Figure 4); also, we would expect to see the cluster analysis with less depth and more mixing among disciplines across domains such that, e.g., disciplines within the humanities domain are not totally separated from disciplines in the STEM domain (Figure 5).

The need for taking stock of the field of risk and crisis communications research and developing these benchmarks is timely and perhaps even overdue. Assessing our current state is imperative as we take steps towards convergence (14-16)—and measure the impact of those steps. We, the risk and crisis communication scholars, face substantive challenges as we seek to employ best practices in risk and crisis communications research.

In addition to our disciplinary silos, structural obstacles are also present challenges. First, we live in an information age where images, words, and ideas are widely available and quickly disseminated, often resulting in information overload, i.e., when the level of information is greater than information processing capacity (17). Thus, the import of identifying a target audience is now coupled with competition for attention in the cacophonous environment of an endless information stream. Second, there are significant structural challenges to risk and crisis communication exacerbated by information overload, including unequal information access, challenges in intergovernmental coordination, concerns of trust and credibility (18), and poor numeracy (19). Third, we now live in the Anthropocene, where human activities are impacting the environment, resulting in novel disaster events (20) and subsequently leading to more complex, interwoven, and multifaceted hazard scenarios.

Risk and crisis communications scholars have minimal power to affect change when it comes to information overload, structural challenges, and implications of living in the Anthropocene. However, we do have agency over how we conduct our studies, where we disseminate them, and how we interact with one another. With studies siloed, advancements in risk and crisis communications are not achieving the broader impacts that the scholarly community desires: to increase human and environmental safety and well-being and mitigate deleterious effects of a disaster. Regardless of our academic upbringings and past work that we have done in our own disciplinary silos, we—and risk and crisis communication scholars writ large—share the common vision of enhancing human and environmental safety with our work. Therefore, it is time to prioritize researching ways to break down these silos and build bridges across scientific disciplines and domains.

Data Availability

Data and code to reproduce our analyses are available on Mendeley Data. The permanent DOI is <https://www.doi.org/10.17632/9jcdz2k2tc>.

Acknowledgments

Portions of this material is based upon work supported by the National Science Foundation under EPSCoR Cooperative Agreement Grant No. OIA-1757351 (AMR). Any opinions, findings, and conclusions or recommendations expressed in this material are those of

the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the views of the National Science Foundation or Department of Homeland Security.

Portions of this research were conducted with the U.S. Department of Homeland Security (DHS) Science and Technology Directorate (S&T) under contract 70RSAT20KPM000150 (AMR, CI, EAS). Any opinions contained herein are those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect those of DHS S&T.

List 1: Communication Management, Crisis Communication, Crisis Perception, Crisis Preparedness, Crisis Tolerance, Crisis Actor, Crisis and Emergency Risk Communication, Crisis Communication Theory, Crisis Emotions, Crisis Framing, Crisis Influence, Crisis Management, Crisis Response, Crisis Type, Crisis Typology, Disaster Communication, Disaster Perception, Disaster Preparedness, Disaster Tolerance, Emergency Risk Communication, Hazard Communication, Hazard Perception, Hazard Preparedness, Hazard Tolerance, Health Communication, Health Crisis, Health Risk, Instructional Risk and Crisis Communication, Interpersonal Communication, Legal Crisis, Megacrisis, Organizational Crisis, Perceived Crisis Severity, Refugee Crisis, Risk Communication, Risk Perception, Risk Preparedness, Risk Tolerance, Risk and Crisis Communication, Situational Crisis Communication Theory, Social-Mediated Crisis, Social-Mediated Crisis Communication, Sports Communication, Stakeholder Communication, Strategic Communication, Transparent Organizational Communication, Water Crisis

Figures

Figure 1. The processes of identifying publications and creating lexicons for disciplines. Letters indicate steps of each process.

Figure 2. The disciplinarity scoring and discipline classification processes for an example publication.

Figure 3. Numbers of publications and outlets with risk and crisis communication keywords versus year. Number of publications (scientific journal articles or conference proceeding papers; blue) and outlets (journal titles or conference proceeding titles; gold) versus year. Publications for the year 2021 are omitted from this graph because data were collected during 2021 and thus we have a partial record for that year.

Figure 4. Number of publications with risk and crisis communication keywords versus the number of outlets (e.g., journals, conference proceedings). Point color corresponds to year of publication in an outlet. Thick black line depicts result of simple linear regression of publication number versus outlet number on an annual basis; grey shading indicates 95% confidence band. Long-dashed line is 1:1 line; short-dashed lines indicate 2:1 and 1:2 lines.

Figure 5. Structure of risk and crisis communication publications according to discipline. Hierarchical clustering of literature on risk and crisis communications with discipline color mapping to domain (STEM, purple; Social Sciences, orange; Humanities, green). Graphic design by Mr. Bratislav “BaTo” Cvijetić VMASC Lead Project Scientist.

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